

Professional Ethics, Organizational Practices, and Culture of Trust by Entrepreneurial Managers of Selected Small and Medium Enterprises in Bulacan

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Abstract:- This paper emphasizes some ethical ways of being a leader and steers for own professional development and growth as entrepreneurial managers. We have witnessed that some organizations have become more diverse in terms of ethical values and those in the business arena are experiencing ethical dilemmas that if not given immediate attention may result to serious complications. Thus, this study likewise emphasizes the necessity to explore ways in which the sample of entrepreneurial managers find their values and behaviors as contributing to the fostering of culture of trust within the organization. This research employed a quantitative-qualitative methods of research. A quantitative-descriptive design is used to observe and measure the variables to identify the different categories of small and medium enterprises in selected municipalities in Bulacan. A qualitative-narrative design is used to conduct an in-depth interview to reconcile conflicting stories and highlight tensions and challenges which can be opportunities for innovation. A narrative survey design, based on the study by Gardiner and Tenuto (2015), was utilized consisting of a semi-structured oral interview process with the key informants from small and medium enterprises in selected municipalities in Bulacan. Data were collected in the form of interviews and professional observations with the entrepreneurial managers, such as business owners, managers, supervisors, and officers-in-charge. Dilemmas reported were analyzed utilizing respondents' ethical values in an organization together with the ethical leadership theories. Results indicated ways how business or organizational leaders can utilize ethical decision-making for organizational improvement and ways to build a culture of trust within the organization.

Keywords:- Professional Ethics; Organizational Practices; Culture of Trust; Entrepreneurial Managers; Small and Medium Enterprises.

I. INTRODUCTION

Professional ethics are principles that govern the behavior of a person or group in a business environment. Like values, professional ethics provide rules on how a person should act towards other people and institutions in such an environment. (Retrieved from

<https://www.iaa.govt.nz/for-advisers/adviser-tools/ethics-toolkit/professional-ethics-and-codes-of-conduct>)

The interest on professional ethics by entrepreneurial managers fostering cultures of trust are considered starting points for writing this study. As educators, our personal and professional experiences led the researchers to investigate and study the perspectives and reflections that provided by entrepreneurial managers of selected Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Bulacan regarding their own ethical behaviors, characteristics, and values.

Entrepreneurial Managers, whether business owners, managers, supervisors, persons-in charge of the business, function, and work as to improve the business operations. He/she is the one who takes care of managing and allocating the resources, leading and supervising employees to ensure productivity and efficiency of operations; thus, providing directions on how best to handle different tasks while maintaining customer satisfaction. They implement strategies that will help generate more revenue or profitability for the business. They hire and manage employees or workers, prepare budgets, work on team building efforts or restructure the organization to affect necessary change. Therefore, there is a need to determine the ethical ways of being and the leading for professional growth and growth as entrepreneurial managers.

➤ Literature Review

Brown and Trevino (2006) defined ethical leadership as “the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making.” Examples of such conduct include openness, honesty, and treating employees fairly and thoughtfully. Social learning theory was used to gain an understanding as to why ethical leadership is important to employees and how it is perceived to work.

Kaptein, M. (2017) defined an ethical leader as “the one who is not only a moral person and a moral manager who demonstrates what is normatively appropriate behavior and follows the current ethical norms. An ethical leader is also a moral entrepreneur who creates new ethical norms.” He argued that there is a third component to ethical

leadership—moral entrepreneurship, in addition to the already defined components of the moral person and the moral manager. His belief is that moral entrepreneurship opens avenues for studying various antecedents and outcomes of ethical leadership that hasn't been acknowledged adequately to date.

Studies of the antecedents of ethical leadership, at both the situational and personal levels, have found that leaders who have had ethical role models are more likely to become ethical leaders. These studies have also found that the personality traits of agreeableness and conscientiousness are positively related to ethical leadership. And studies on corporate social responsibility are concerned with how companies can contribute to societal development, not only in the sense of solving social problems, but also in the sense of improving social welfare, promoting social progress, and creating new social value.

Philippine Business (2019) revealed that more Filipinos today are starting their own businesses. These new entrepreneurs come from diverse backgrounds and a wide range of ages – from college students to retirees, and everyone in between. No matter their background or the kind of business they put up, new entrepreneurs are likely to face similar challenges such as lack of funding, cash flow concerns, and lack of management skills. Thus, to start your own venture, you need to be prepared for these challenges and create a plan to address them.

The dictionary defines ethical issues as “the study of standards of conduct and moral judgment; moral philosophy, a treatise on this study or the system or code of morals of a particular person, religion, group or profession.”

Ethical issues in business is a situation where a moral conflict arises and must be addressed. In other words, it is an occasion where a moral standard is questioned. Ethical issues occur when a given decision, scenario or activity creates a conflict with a society's moral principles. Both individuals and businesses can be involved in these conflicts since any of their activities might be put to question from an ethical standpoint. Individuals are subject to these issues in their relationships with other individuals or in their relationships with organizations and same goes for organizations. (Retrieved from <https://www.myaccountingcourse.com/accountingdictionary/ethical>).

According to a business dictionary an “entrepreneur” is a person who is trained to take initiative by organizing a business to take benefit of a specific opportunity when he comes across it and decides what, how, and how much of a good or service will be produced. An takes the risks who will do anything to win. He will always keep an eye on what is happening under his supervision by monitoring and controlling all the business activities. But according to economist Joseph Alois Schumpeter, entrepreneurs are not entirely motivated by profit but they regard their as a standard for measuring achievement or success being their way to prove the society in which they live in that can do a “thing” better than anyone else.

Entrepreneur managers can create and control change within the organization. This means they are responsible in solving problems, generating new ideas, and implementing them. It also involves allocating funds, as well as assigning staff and other organizational resources. Entrepreneurial leadership involves organizing and motivating a group of people to achieve a common objective through innovation, risk optimization, taking advantage of opportunities, and managing the dynamic organizational environment. The traditional corporate mindset has its focus on systems and processes, whereas the entrepreneurial style is more risk oriented.

Indeed Career Guide (2021) stated that “Ethical leadership demonstrates a high regard for values”. The principles of ethical leadership include honesty, justice, respect, community and integrity-- it is critical to the success of any business. Ethical leaders should demonstrate ethical and appropriate behavior in every facet of their life over time, even when their behavior is not necessarily observable by their employees. Ethical leadership may even occasionally be unpleasant, for example when it involves terminating an employee who uses company property for personal ends. Nevertheless, maintaining your integrity is of paramount importance to leadership. Ethical leaders also work to create an ethical work culture. This means that a work environment is governed by a fair, clearly articulated set of rules, rather than by personality or politics. In an ethical work culture, an organization's management articulates a set of principles that are understood, and bought in to, by everyone in the organization.

➤ *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

Fig 1 Professional Ethics, Organizational Practices, and Culture of Trust by Entrepreneurial Managers of Selected Small and Medium Enterprises in Bulacan

Figure 1 presents the Independent Variables (IV) which consist of professional ethics and organizational practices by entrepreneurial managers. The Dependent Variables (DV) which consist of culture of trust in an organization leading to success.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

The primary goals of the study are to identify some ethical ways of being and leading for own professional development and growth as entrepreneurial managers. The secondary goal of the study is to explore ways in which the sample of entrepreneurial managers find their behaviors as contributing to the fostering of culture of trust.

II. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

➤ *Subject*

This study involved the 29 participants from selected small and medium enterprises in Bulacan: Baliuag, Malolos, Marilao, Meycauayan, and San Jose Del Monte. Respondents are business owners, managers, supervisors, and officers-in-charge of the participating businesses. It allowed the researchers to draw more precise conclusions by ensuring that participants are from small and medium enterprises and properly represented by selected municipalities in Bulacan.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Profile

Profile of the Respondents in terms of Small and Medium Enterprise				
MUNICIPALITY	SME's CATEGORY		FREQUENCY	PERCENT
	Small	Medium		
Baliwag	5	1	6	20.69
Malolos	4	1	5	17.24
Marilao	4	2	6	20.69
Meycauayan	5	0	5	17.24
San Jose Del Monte	5	2	7	24.14
TOTAL	23	6	29	100%

SMEs – Small and Medium Enterprises

Table 1 shows that the participating businesses were dominated by Small Enterprises with 23 respondents and Medium Enterprises were 6 respondents respectively. San Jose Del Monte City has the highest frequency of 7 or 24.14 percent of respondents and the least are Malolos and Meycauayan with 5 or 17.24 percent of respondents. There were face-to-face interactions during the conduct of the study, since the interview questionnaires were administered personally by the proponents, and the responses were

monitored and checked if all questions were answered religiously by the participating respondents.

➤ *Instrument*

This study used a quantitative-qualitative methods of research. A quantitative-descriptive design is used to observe and measure the variables in order to identify the categories of small and medium enterprises in selected municipalities in Bulacan. A qualitative-narrative design is used to conduct an in-depth interviews to reconcile

conflicting stories and highlight tensions and challenges which can be opportunities for innovation. The interview questionnaire is based on the study by Gardiner and Tenuto (2015). They utilized a narrative survey design consisting of a semi-structured oral interview process with their participants to elicit personal narratives, reflections, perceptions, thoughts, ideas, and visions. Narrative surveys can involve the oral speech, observations by the proponents, written notes, shared experience, history, and story-telling from key informants.

The proponents investigated the professional ethics, as well as the organizational practices by selected entrepreneurial managers using the assessment form adapted from Gardiner and Tenuto (2015), utilized constructed questions and encouraged oral narratives from their participants. Gardiner and Tenuto's (2015) analysis revealed patterns and themes in their participants' orations and ethical dilemmas as well as decision-making processes of the participants. The results can identify entrepreneurial managers' codes of ethics, leadership dilemmas, and ethical decision-making.

• *Gardiner and Tenuto (2015). Interview Questions Include:*

- ✓ In your opinion, what are the necessary values of an ethical entrepreneurial managers?
- ✓ Do you believe there are specific behaviors or characteristics that define an ethical leader?
- ✓ What kind of ethical challenges do you encounter as an entrepreneurial manager and what are some of the practices that you employ to solve them?
- ✓ Can you tell me about a time when you faced an ethical dilemma in your leadership role and what worked or did not work in solving the problem?
- ✓ What are some of the ways that you have tried to build a culture of trust?
- ✓ Are there any ethical leaders who have influenced or inspired you?

Two case scenarios were asked from the participants for a comprehensive analysis of the data gathered by the proponents.

- *A long-time colleague of yours has misappropriated substantial funds from the company's budget for personal gain. You have knowledge of your colleague's financial duress on a personal basis and are aware of this behavior on your colleague's part. How would you deal with this problem on a personal and/or professional basis?*
- ✓ Anonymously contact police or tell your colleague's supervisor.
- ✓ Discuss directly with your colleague and encourage him to admit and seek help.
- ✓ Stay quiet and not say anything hoping someone else will find out.
- ✓ Other.

- *You are working with an entrepreneurial manager or owner who has "power over" you and openly displays racist behavior. You have tried to convey that you do not condone the behavior. The manager's behavior is specifically directed at other colleagues in your company and seems to be escalating. You are aware that these colleagues are afraid to complain on a more formal basis. What is your ethical responsibility in this situation?*

- ✓ None. Ignore the situation as it does not directly involve you.
- ✓ Discuss directly with your colleague about how the group of colleagues feels.
- ✓ Discuss privately with the colleague and inform them of support/complaint processes.
- ✓ Other.

➤ *Data Collection Procedures*

The mode of data gathering was the interview questionnaire method administered personally by the proponents. In gathering the pertinent data for this study, the proponents carried out the following procedures:

- Inquired/Asked Recommendation For The Best Key Informants For This Study From The Business Permit Licensing Office (BPLO) Of Each Municipality;
- Sent A Request Letter To Registered Small And Medium Enterprises Of Selected Municipalities To Conduct An Interview And Observation;
- Employed The Ethics Of Research, The Health And Safety Protocols During Interviews; And
- Gathered And Analyzed The Information/Data From The Key Informants.

➤ *Data Analysis*

The data gathered in this study were carefully analyzed by the proponents to identify the patterns and themes in the respondents' orations, in terms of, the necessary values for an ethical entrepreneurial managers (managers, supervisors, persons-in-charge of the business), characteristics, challenges encountered, and their practices in solving them, ethical dilemma, building culture of trust, ethical persons who have influenced them and case scenarios. The study also provided the implications of the findings towards the fostering and building of cultures of trust. Each interview was transcribed and analyzed by the proponents to search for occurring repeatedly and similar ethical aspects, considerations, and practices. Each interview was further reviewed looking for recurring themes of ethical behaviors, characteristics, and values of the respondents.

➤ *Ethical Consideration*

In adherence and observance of ethical standards set for research undertaking involving the request letter to Business Licensing Office (BPLO) for the registered Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in their municipalities; the Agreed Informed Consent form approved and signed by the key informants prior to the conduct of interview; and the request letter of invitation to participating enterprises, so as to proceed to the conduct of interview.

The interview survey questionnaire instrument, by Gardiner and Tenuto (2015), does not required a letter to use this assessment as any researcher can use this assessment tool for research purposes. Moreover, following the ethics of research, key informants' responses were voluntarily, treated confidentially, and they may withdraw their responses anytime should they preferred confidentiality of

their data. Hence, the confidentiality of the information supplied by the key informants was respected and the researchers will do everything in their power to protect the anonymity of the participants. Further, the business name and the personal identity of the key informants will not be published without their consent.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to most of the key informants who are entrepreneurial managers representing their business firms as owners/store managers/supervisors/officers-in-charge from selected small and medium enterprises in Bulacan, they identified having respect as the topmost, followed by having knowledge and being honest, next are being considerate and transparent, risk-taker and approachable.

The least are identified being a law-abiding citizen, adaptable, persistent, determined, observant, concerned, consistent, having a pleasing personality, and good in communication as values that are necessary for an ethical entrepreneurial managers should own as shown on the figure below.

Fig 2 Necessary Values of an Ethical Entrepreneurial Managers

A. *Do you Believe there are Specific Behaviors or Characteristics that Define an Ethical Leader?*

The table below shows that majority of the respondents answered *Yes* (25 or 86.21 percent) believed that there are specific behaviors or characteristics that define an ethical leader. These specific behaviors or characteristics are professionalism, a good listener, with a strong influence, experience, and skills, knows how to develop people's potentials, humble or low-profile, accountable, a role model, strict to policies, and possess moral values.

Only one respondent answered *None*, believing that there are leadership virtues that are common to many that make an almost standard definition.

Table 2 Do you Believe there are Specific Behaviors or Characteristics that Define an Ethical Entrepreneurial Manager?

YES		NONE		NO ANSWER		TOTAL	
F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
25	86.21	1	3.45	3	10.34	29	100

B. *What Kind of Ethical Challenges do you Encounter as an Entrepreneurial Manager and what are Some of the Practices that you Employ to Solve them?*

➤ *Ethical Challenges Encountered by Entrepreneurial Managers and their Practices in Solving them*

Some of the ethical challenges encountered by the key informants are challenges in the management of the

employees and their differences, married employees having an affair or immorality, staff moving out due to job opportunities abroad, maintain customers satisfaction, connection with the suppliers, and others; adhering to rules and maintaining a harmonious relationship with others; and adapting to changes. And the practices that these entrepreneurial managers, such as to communicate well with the right people, influencing the workplace by advancing an

organizational climate that expects individuals to carry out their tasks with a great respect for honesty and integrity, and following the rules and policies of the organizations.

C. *Can you Tell me About a Time when you Faced an Ethical Dilemma in your Leadership Role and what Worked or did not Work in Solving the Problem?*

➤ *Ethical Dilemma in your Leadership Role*

Most of the key informants experienced confidential dilemmas which takes time to solve. They also stated that discussing with those they trust helps as well as finding and seeking facts versus opinions and hearsay. Two of the key informants also added that choosing between following orders that are not aligned with their perspectives, morals and beliefs is really a difficult situation and is hard to get out from.

Misunderstanding about work inventory, division of work, letting toxic clients go due to misunderstanding are added dilemmas faced by the key informants. Another one from a small enterprise gave an example that he encountered recently. This was regarding an employee doing unethical accounting practices, the employee explained her side but admitted her mistakes too. These are an example of the dilemma they experienced as entrepreneurial managers in which they have to bridge between the top management and the employees. Also added was that there should be a balance between the two. Further, evaluation, open forum, and proper communication are the cited solutions by most of the key informants to promote good relationship between the management and the employees.

D. *What are Some of the Ways that you have Tried to Build a Culture of Trust?*

➤ *Ways to Build a Culture of Trust*

The key informants cited a few ways on how to build a culture of trust within their organizations and these are the following:

- Proper communication, open forum, know your team, remove the barriers, and keep cordial relationship despite issues within the organization. Put yourself in their shoes.
- Implement quality and consistency in the rules and regulations of the company.
- Show that you trust your employees, respect their rights, to gain their trust too.
- Express empathy, concern, and listen to the needs of your employees.
- Employ transparency. The respondents stated that if you are honest to your employees, it will reciprocate back to the manager.
- Give constructive criticisms to improve their work and skills and believe in their potentials.
- Show dedication to the job, as well as to the employees. Treat everyone with respect and fairness.
- Participative management. A type of leadership wherein employees are encouraged to give their inputs on most of the organization decisions.

E. *Are there any Ethical Leaders who have Influenced or Inspired you?*

➤ *Ethical Leaders who have Influenced Educational Leaders*

Most of the key informants answered the business owners where they work, followed by their families, and customers. Others have their own inspirations, and these are the following:

• *Jesus Christ*

He was a listening leader. Because he loved others with a perfect love, he listened without being condescending. A great leader listens not only to others, but also to his conscience and to the promptings of God. Jesus was a patient, pleading, loving leader.

Retrieved from <https://www.churchofjesuschrist.org> › *ensign* › 1979/08

• *Mahatma Gandhi*

Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi is widely recognized as one of the twentieth century's greatest political and spiritual leaders. Honored in India as the father of the nation, he pioneered and practiced the principle of Satyagraha—resistance to tyranny through mass nonviolent civil disobedience.

Retrieved from <https://www.youthforhumanrights.org> › *mahatma-gandhi*

• *Henry Sy*

He was known as the "father of modern Philippine retail". He developed ShoeMart into SM Investments, one of the largest malls in the Philippines. He also founded BDO Unibank and real estate. For eleven straight years until his death, Sy was named by Forbes as the richest person in the Philippines.

Retrieved from https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henry_Sy

• *Robert Kiyosaki*

He developed transformational, situational, and participatory leadership skills in managing operations at the Cashflow Technologies Company through life time experiences.

Retrieved from <https://studycorgi.com/robert-kiyosakis-leadership-style>

• *Luigi Vera Jr.*

The managing director of Am-Phil Group, the corporate vehicle behind Chili's and other brands. Retrieved from <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/manila-bulletin/20170322/281994672311695>

• *Francis Kong*

The President of Success Options Inc. and Director of Inspire Leadership Consultancy One of the most respected business speakers in the country, Francis Kong is a recipient of the Outstanding Filipino (TOFIL) Award 2014. Francis is

a columnist, and his column at the Philippine Star has been awarded best business column for the years 2009, 2010, 2013, 2014 and 2015 and has been accorded hall of fame awardee by the catholic mass media awards.

Retrieved from <https://inspireleaders.com.ph/resource-person/francis-kong>

• **BTS K-Pop Band**

The key informant is inspired by them for the group’s good ethics and for being effective artists.

BTS stands for Bangtan Sonyeondan. It is also known as the Bangtan Boys. It is a seven-member South Korean boy band formed in 2013 in Seoul. Bangtan Sonyeondan in Korean means "bulletproof boy scouts." Koreans call them by this name, however people in other countries refer to them as BTS. *Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BTS>*

➤ **Opinions on the Following Case Scenarios**

The following case scenarios were discussed with the key informants and were asked to give their opinions accordingly.

- A long-time colleague of yours has misappropriated substantial funds from the company’s budget for personal gain. You have knowledge of your colleague’s financial duress on a personal basis and are aware of this behavior on your colleague’s part. How would you deal with this problem on a personal and/or professional basis?
- Anonymously contact police or tell your colleague’s supervisor.
- Discuss directly with your colleague and encourage him to admit and seek help.
- Stay quiet and not say anything hoping someone else will find out.
- Other.

Fig 2 Case Scenario No. 1

Figure 2 shows that majority of the respondents have the same opinion with option B and said that they will discuss it with their colleague and encourage them to admit and seek help, with 21 or 72.41 percent of the respondents. The said respondents would do this in order their colleague to stop his or her wrong doings. They also added that they will advise the person not to do it again. On the other hand, two of the respondents or 6.90 percent said that they will anonymously contact police or tell your colleague’s supervisor. And 2 of the respondents said that he will perform other methods such as telling it to the business owner himself and have him given a memo warning, while 4 of the respondents have no answer on this case scenario.

- *You are working with an entrepreneurial manager or owner who has “power over” you and openly displays racist behavior. You have tried to convey that you do not condone the behavior. The manager’s behavior is specifically directed at other colleagues in your company and seems to be escalating. You are aware that these colleagues are afraid to complain on a more formal basis. What is your ethical responsibility in this situation?*
- ✓ None. Ignore the situation as it does not directly involve you.
- ✓ Discuss directly with your colleague about how the group of colleagues feels.
- ✓ Discuss privately with the colleague and inform them of support/complaint processes.
- ✓ Other.

Fig 3 Case Scenario No. 2

Figure 3 shows that most of the key informants chose option B, to discuss it directly with their colleague about how the group must feel, with 13 or 44.83 percent. The key informants also stated that the issue should be discussed on meetings without pointing fingers or name dropping on anyone. Followed by option C, to discuss privately with the colleague and inform them of support/complaint processes, with 10 or 34.48 percent, option A with 2 or 6.90 percent, to do nothing and just ignore the situation as it does not directly involve you.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of this study, there were 29 key informants who are store owners, managers, supervisors, and officers-in-charge of selected small and medium enterprises from 4 municipalities in Bulacan, namely: Baliuag, Malolos, Marilao, Meycauayan, and San Jose Del Monte Bulacan respectively.

➤ *As to the Findings, Based on the Narrative Interviews, are Concluded as Follows:*

The key informants identified having respect, knowledge, being honest, considerate, and transparent, risk-taker, and approachable. Others are identified being a law-abiding citizen, adaptable, persistent, determined, observant, concerned, consistent, having a pleasing personality, and good in communication as values that are necessary for an ethical entrepreneurial manager.

Majority of the key informants believed that there are specific behaviors or characteristics that define an ethical leader. These specific behaviors or characteristics are professionalism, a good listener, with a strong influence, experience, and skills, knows how to develop people’s potentials, humble or low-profile, accountable, a role model, strict to policies, and possess moral values.

The key informants cited some of the ethical challenges they encountered such as challenges in the management of the employees and their differences, married employees having an affair or immorality, staff moving out due to job opportunities abroad, maintain customers satisfaction, connection with the suppliers, and others; adhering to rules and maintaining a harmonious relationship with others; and adapting to changes. The key informants

also cited some of the practices that they are doing, such as, to communicate well with the right people, influencing the workplace by advancing an organizational climate that expects individuals to carry out their tasks with a great respect for honesty and integrity and following the rules and policies of the organizations.

Most of the key informants experienced confidential dilemmas which takes time to solve. They also stated that discussing with those they trust helps as well as finding and seeking facts versus opinions and hearsay and choosing between following orders that are not aligned with their perspectives, morals and beliefs is really a difficult situation and is hard to get out from.

To build a culture of trust within their organization, the key informants determined proper communication, open forum, know your team, remove the barriers, and keep cordial relationship despite issues within the organization. Also stated, implement quality and consistency in the rules and regulations of the company. show that you trust your employees, respect their rights, to gain their trust too. express empathy, concern, and listen to the needs of your employees, transparency, constructive criticisms, show dedication to the job, as well as to the employees, treat everyone with respect and fairness, and employ a participative management.

Two case scenarios were discussed with the key informants and were asked to give their opinions accordingly. For the case scenario 1, regarding a colleague misappropriating substantial amount that they are aware with, majority of the key informants stated that they will discuss it with their colleague and encourage them to admit and seek help. The latter will do this for their colleague to

stop his or her wrong doings. They also added that they will advise the person not to do it again. For the case scenario 2, about a leader who is openly displays racist behavior directed to minority group of colleagues in their company, majority of the key informants have answered that they will discuss it directly with their colleague about how the group must feel. One key informant further stated that the issue should be discussed on meetings without pointing fingers or name dropping on anyone.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers offered the following recommendations based on the findings and conclusions revealed in the study.

Accordingly, ethical leadership means that individuals behave according to a set of principles and values that are recognized by the majority as a sound basis for the common good. These include integrity, respect, trust, fairness, transparency, and honesty. An ethical leaders must be accountable for any actions, take charge, and shape the present and future through their words and deeds. Ethical leaders are present in good and bad times, develop their teams, and defend others when needed. Hence, it is recommended to the entrepreneurial managers that they may truly and deeply live out the real values of being professional and ethical leaders. In fact, professionalism entails moral ascendancy.

They may reflect on the following: (a) Honesty is not just about telling the truth. It is about being real with yourself and others about who you are, what you want and what you need to live your most authentic life. Honesty promotes openness, empowers us, and enables us to develop consistency in how one presents the facts. (b) The key to leadership is to lead with love. Leading with love means knowing and caring about what inspires and empowers people. It is about caring enough to know what is important to them and helping them succeed. (c) Work-driven leaders can do more than define purpose at work. They can connect with their team and motivate them to care about a cause, too. Work-driven leaders care about their team as people. (d) Being compassionate can encourage healthy relationships as well as can ensure a more empathetic work environment. Compassionate leaders always put others needs before their own. They create a tuning with other thoughts and feelings. (e) God fearing leaders keep a positive attitude. There are many occasions, where a leader could have lost his/her cool when things do not go the way they were planned. However, they may show how to keep a positive attitude and focus on God, despite the tough circumstances. (f) True leaders work with others to translate their knowledge into initiatives that benefit their organization. They show the way through their actions and behavior. In leadership, however, discipline creates power. (g) Lastly, discipline leads to more flexibility and control over your every aspect of your life. Discipline creates great leaders.

Accordingly, ethical dilemmas can be resolved through effective decision-making. An ethical dilemma requires a person to define right from wrong. In any dilemma, the following steps are recommended which a leader can take to resolve it. This is called the RIGHT Decision Method: (a) The first step is **R**ecognize the ethical dilemma being faced. All dilemmas have the same form: “If I do A, I will get negative consequence X, If I do B, I will get negative consequence Y” (b) The second step is **I**dentify points of view in the situation. This means considering the viewpoint of the person receiving services, your colleagues, other parties involved, etc. Restating the problem clearly to someone else can also help a leader check out whether he interpreted the situation accurately. It is important to understand how the person receiving supports feels. (c) the third step is **G**ather resources and assistance. Now that a leader has an accurate understanding for the problem and various perspectives, this step encourages him to consider other people who may be able to assist him. A leader may also need to find important information from other agencies, legal services, and community resources. (d) the fourth step is **H**ave a plan. Formulating a plan will help a leader decide the best way to put his ideas into action. Once he considered the following issues, he has to write a plan down and identify step-by-step actions that he plan to take. (e) Lastly is to **T**ake action based on ethical standards. The fifth and final step is implementing the plan a leader developed in the manner he decided. Then, it is important to monitor its success using the success indicators he identified in the planning process to help him reflect on his decision.

To any case scenarios especially in their respective businesses, it is important that a leader may remain transparent in everything, consistent with company policies, knows a proper way of communication, living out a participative management a way to build a culture of trust within the organization. Just like some influential leaders, who possessed the unique and exceptional traits of a leader, they may opt to follow the examples of these people as an inspiration for being professional-ethical leaders. As Mahatma Gandhi fights without the use of violence, leaders should do the same. As Jesus Christ altruistically loves the humankind, leaders should love their work and subordinates by giving themselves without anything in return. Lastly, as like as Pope Francis - a man of simplicity and humility, leaders are called to be simple and humble servant leaders of our society, too.

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